

Future of Work: Advancing Equity and Work Life Balance for women in Emerging work Model

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Abstract

The new era came up with lots of challenges and opportunities for working women. The future is being shaped by technological disruption, different work force expectation and expanding area of flexible work arrangement. As these Ensuring fairness especially for women is important during changes. Emerging work models such as remote work, hybrid work and gig – based work affect women’s participation, work life balance and progression. On the other hand it also impacts the male counter parts but it shows a huge impact on the female employees. Women’s are working in different areas and at different position but need to maintain the balance in personal and professional life. New technologies have impacted women’s life both in positive and negative ways. This paper explores impact of emerging work models and highlights both challenges and opportunities while proposing solution for fostering gender equality in fast changing work environment.

Key word: work, working women, equity, Work Life Balance, work model

INTRODUCTION

In recent era work is changing very rapidly due to fast changing technology, work culture due to globalization and societal shift. To cope up with these changes flexible work models come in to view to fulfill these requirements. It also have its own limitations, advantages and shortcoming. for women who are already bearing a burden of profession and personal life – future of work hold new potential for self efficacy and contribution . Women have still facing challenges in job role, societal identity and equality. Flexible work models have some where assist the women in positive ways and on other side it’s also contribute new challenges of learning and a skill development. Technological advancement helps her to manage things but at same time it come with 24x7 work for her professional work.

Flexible work culture helps women to take care about her personal life and spend quality time with loved ones, somewhere while focusing on the family she need to give her best output to her organisation to maintain her career growth. This new era somewhere blurring the bounders of male and female at work place and focusing on equitable work culture but, women need to fulfill the requirements of her personal life.

This paper looks at influence of emerging work model on gender equality and possible solution for fair practice and comprehensive future of work.

Study objectives

1. To study the impact of flexi work model on gender equality
2. To analyze the factors influencing the future work models

3. To study possible solution for work life balance, equality and participation

gradation and work life balance practice which motivate employee and reduce work stress.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

1. According to the Bhatt, Narayani in their study found that, prolonged working hours, rigid work policies and work burden are the reasons for stress, work life imbalance and high attrition rate at organization. They suggest that Indian IT companies come up with new policies and flexible work culture to avoid stress and attrition at work place.
2. According to the Adhikari, Amrapali- in their study on flexibility and diversity at work place in Indian companies suggested that managing work force diversity is management function, its responsibility of management to analyze the contribution of work force and manage the diversity.
3. According to Dr. Payal Mahendrasinh Mahida, Ms. Suchita Chauhan in their research work found that there are various organisational and family factors are responsible for work life balance of working women in different sectors. These factors are career growth, family responsibility, working hours, work pressure, parental and home responsibility, etc.
4. A study on work – family life imbalance among women administrators in UAE higher education institution found that work life imbalance have deep influence of social and family structure and its related values. For this organisation need to put continuous efforts to find and implement effective HR practice to reduce the work related pressure. It important for organisation to incorporate hybrid work arrangement technological up

Factors influencing balance and equity

There are various factors which create impact on balance and equity is as follow

1. Societal factors - various norms, rules, regulation at society also contribute towards women equality and working.
2. Economical factors - utilization of various resources are needed to utilize in proper way to establish equity.
3. Technological factors – technological up gradation and gaps in skills to use them create barriers to women.
4. Family role – the role of women at her home impacts the growth and equality at large
5. Organization culture - male dominated work culture hinder the success of women at work place

Statement of the problem

Advancing Equity and Work Life Balance for women in Emerging work Model

Research design -

The present study adopted descriptive type of research approach

Population – working women in different institutions and organizations

Sample – for the data collection sample of 50 women have drawn

Tools used for the study – primary data was collected through questionnaire

Secondary data was collected through internet, website, journals etc

Emerging Work models and their impact –

There are different work models which have various impacts on work.

1. **Hybrid work** – it is a big shift from the old model of work. It consists of work in office and work from home. It consists of flexibility to work in different dimensions and as per the requirement of organization and employee. Most of the companies have shifted towards this and gaining benefits. This model helps the women to manage balance in between the work and family
2. **Gig work** – it is kind work where worker work to any short term work. It also include independent project and freelance work. There is no single work force in gig work. Most of the educated people are part of gig economy/work. This model have its own advantages and disadvantages. gig economy provide flexibility but somehow it provide fixed income source. For women it also provide huge platform to utilize skill and talent to become independent.

Both above models have its own impact on work. Hybrid work create disadvantage in term of in equality at work place. Office worker gain more growth and leadership opportunity.

Gig economy provides flexibility but cannot provide formal security and upward mobility.

Challenges to equity and Balance

It may found that male dominated leadership, biased compensation structure and difference in work assignment can cause the hurdles to career growth for women. Household responsibilities and gig economy creates limitation for income and stability. Technological advancement has created a challenge to learn and

implement new skills to sustain at work place. Remote work culture also makes women more stressful and impacts her mental health.

Opportunities of emerging work models-

1. Hybrid work

- Hybrid work model created platform for employee to work in a way which is most effective for them.
- It reduce the burnout and stress and comes with more output
- Improved work life balance and efficient use of time.

Gig work-

- Gig work provides independence to worker. This is a plat form where they can manage their work from their home place or any other setting
- Gig workers have flexibility to choose their working hours. They have freedom to complete the task within deadline by their own strategy.
- Its great opportunity for independent and extra earning

Analysis and interpretation of data

1. Do you need flexible work hours

As shown in the figure most of the employees said yes that they need flexible work hour

2. Do you think flexible work hour's helps for work life balance

90 % of the employees agreed that flexible work hours helps to maintain work life balance

3. Do you think that work life balance improve employee productivity

As per the graph shown below it is find that most of employees agree that work life balance helps to improve work productivity.

4. Are you aware about gig economy

Some of the women employee are aware about gig economy and few said no

5. Do you think flexible work helps to maintain equity at work place

Most of the women employees agree that flexible work helps to maintain equity **FINDING**

1. Most of the women need flexible work hour.
2. Flexible work hour helps women to manage their work life balance
3. Flexible work hour helps women to improve their productivity at work place.
4. Gig economy is new concept of work for few women
5. Flexible work hour helps to maintain equity at work place.

Suggestion

1. Organization should consider the women contribution at work place and provide them opportunities for growth and equity.
2. Work life balance is crucial aspect of work, organization should adopt new models and policies for fair practice.

CONCLUSION

Emerging work models are need of today work force. Women employees gain benefits from these work models. Flexible work hours and gig economy helps the women to empower herself. It provides independence and balance between work and profession.

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Graph 1: showing need of flexible work hours

Graph 2: showing need of flexible work hours for work life balance

Graph 3: work life balance improve employee productivity

Graph 4: awareness about gig economy

